

FATIGUE BEHAVIOUR OF YBCO COATED CONDUCTOR WITH Cu LAYER AT 77K

M. Hojo^{1*}, Y. Yoshida¹, M. Sugano², T. Adachi¹, Y. Inoue¹,
K. Shikimachi³, N. Hirano³ and S. Nagaya³

¹Department of Mechanical Engineering and Science, Kyoto University
Sakyo-ku, Kyoto 606-8501, Japan

* hojo_cm@mech.kyoto-u.ac.jp

²Department of Electrical Engineering and Science, Kyoto University
Nishikyo-ku, Kyoto 615-8510, Japan

³Chubu Electric Power Co., Inc.

Midori-ku, Nagoya 459-8522, Japan

SUMMARY

We carried out fatigue tests of YBCO high-temperature superconducting coated conductor with Hastelloy substrate and additional Cu layer in LN₂, together with the measurement of the critical current. The addition of a Cu layer increased the fatigue strength by about 19%. This increase was higher than that for the static properties (5%).

Keywords: YBCO coated conductor, Composite superconductor, Fatigue fracture, Hastelloy substrate, Critical current

INTRODUCTION

YBCO coated conductors are composed of thin yttrium-oxide high-temperature superconducting layer (YBa₂Cu₃O_{7-δ}, YBCO, 1 μm), buffer layers and Hastelloy substrate (100 μm) [1]. Then, the structure of YBCO is one kind of composite material which is composed of a load carrying metallic part (Hastelloy) and a functional ceramic part (YBCO). Since YBCO is brittle oxide, its mechanical properties together with electrical properties is critical for the industrial applications.

YBCO coated conductors are expected to be applied as high T_c superconducting coils used in superconducting magnetic energy storage, SMES, because the conductor has superior transport properties even under a high magnetic field [1-3]. A newly developed YBCO coated conductor with an additional Cu layer is a promising candidate for use as SMES coils. The additional Cu layer, which enhances the thermal and electrical stability of the conductor, enables SMES coils to operate at a temperature of as high as 20-40 K using the conduction cooling method. This conductor with a Cu layer is anticipated to exhibit different transport and mechanical properties from that without a Cu layer.

In the high field involved in SMES, hoop stress due to a Lorentz force is applied to the coated conductor in the longitudinal direction. In the operation of SMES, the current and magnetic field change during the charge/discharge, and cyclic stresses are applied to the conductor tapes. Since the stress level is as high as the load corresponding to the

yield stress of the Hastelloy substrate used in coated conductors, we should investigate the possible fatigue fracture of the YBCO coated conductor with an additional Cu layer.

It is expected that the additional Cu layer, which brings about higher tensile strength than that without the layer, can also result in the higher fatigue strength of the coated conductor. On the other hand, fatigue cracks can initiate from the additional Cu layer because of its low yield stress. Since many slip bands were observed on an Ag layer in a YBCO coated conductor after fatigue tests, fatigue damage in the Cu layer probably affects on the fatigue property of whole coated conductor [4]. Moreover, fatigue cracks initiated in the Cu component and propagated up to the final fracture of Nb₃Al and Nb-Ti composite superconductors [5,6]. However, limited information on the fatigue property and its relation to critical current is available for this coated conductor. Thus, we investigated the possible onset of fatigue cracks from the Cu layer.

In the present study, we carried out tensile tests and fatigue tests on a YBCO coated conductor with and without an additional Cu layer in LN₂ by measuring the critical current, I_c , at the specific strain and after a specific numbers of fatigue cycles, respectively. The fatigue fracture mechanism is discussed on the basis of the microscopic observation of fracture surfaces, the change in I_c during fatigue cycles, and the change in stress of each component.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The base YBCO coated conductor was fabricated through metal organic chemical vapor deposition (MOCVD) process [7]. The conductor includes a buffer layer formed by ion-beam-assisted deposition (IBAD)-Gd₂Zr₂O₇ (1 μm) and pulsed laser deposition (PLD)-CeO₂ (0.4 μm) grown on a Hastelloy C-276 substrate (100 μm). As a stabilizing layer, Ag (10 μm) was deposited on the YBCO (1 μm) film. The YBCO coated conductors with a Cu layer used in this study were obtained by attaching Cu tape (100 μm) to the YBCO coated conductor by passing through a solder bath at about 420 K. The schematic structure is shown in Fig. 1. The Cu tape was positioned on Ag layer side of YBCO coated conductor. The above values in parentheses indicate the nominal thickness of each component. The total thickness and width of the YBCO coated conductor with the Cu layer were about 220 μm and 10 mm, respectively. We hereafter refer to the YBCO coated conductor and the YBCO coated conductor with the additional Cu layer as YBCO composite and Cu/YBCO composite, respectively.

Tensile tests and fatigue tests were carried out using a computer-controlled servo-hydraulic fatigue testing machine (Shimadzu EHF-ED-1, capacity: 9.8 kN). The sample length and gage length were 140 mm and 50 mm, respectively. GFRP tabs were bonded onto the specimen with epoxy adhesive for stress relaxation and insulation. The loading apparatus used to grip the specimens had a serrated surface. All tests were carried out at 77 K by immersing the specimens in LN₂ as shown in Fig. 2.

Tensile static tests were carried out at a strain speed of $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Strain was measured using Nyilas-type double extensometers with a gage length of 25 mm [8,9]. Tensile fatigue tests were carried out under the load controlled mode. The stress ratio, R , of the minimum to the maximum load was kept constant at 0.5 during each test. The stress ratio used in this study corresponds to the stress waveform generated in the conductor in the SMES coil. The frequency of stress cycling was 30 Hz for all tests.

Fig. 1. Schematic structure of YBCO composite with additional Cu layer.

Fig. 2. Schematic of loading apparatus and critical current measurement at 77K.

Voltage-current, $V-I$, curves were measured by the four-probe method at 77 K in a self field during tensile static and fatigue tests. The critical current, I_c , was determined by the definition of $1 \mu\text{V}/\text{cm}$ criterion. The length between the voltage taps was 30 mm. In the measurement of I_c under tensile loading, applied strain was increased by 0.03 % at each step, and I_c was measured at each stage. Moreover, the load was reduced to 20 N between each step and I_c was measured to investigate the reversibility of I_c . At this unloading step, I_c corresponding to the irreversible degradation, was defined by a decrease from the initial value, I_{c0} , of more than 0.5 %. I_c measurements during the fatigue tests were carried out by temporarily stopping the fatigue test after a specific cycles, and at the static loading of 20 N (corresponding to the state of without loading).

Fracture surfaces were observed using a scanning electron microscope (JSM-5410LS) and a field- emission scanning electron microscope (JSM-6500F).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tensile Property of Cu/YBCO and YBCO Composites

Fig. 3 shows the relationship between load and strain applied to the Cu/YBCO and YBCO composites and a bare Hastelloy substrate, which was used for Cu/YBCO and YBCO composites, as a reference. The Hastelloy substrate in the composites and the bare Hastelloy substrate were fabricated through the same batch process. Here, the Hastelloy substrates in the composite tapes have the same thickness, resulting in a different total thickness of the two composite tapes. Fig. 3 shows the tensile properties of composites with the same Hastelloy substrate thickness and a different total tape thickness. Although the thickness of the Cu/YBCO composite is almost twice that of the YBCO composite, the load-strain curve of the Cu/YBCO composite is similar to that of the YBCO composite. These curves indicate that the Hastelloy substrate supports almost all of the load applied to the composites [4]. For Cu/YBCO and YBCO composites, the

tensile loads at 0.9% strain, $F_{0.9\%strain}$, were 1850 N and 1770 N, respectively. The additional Cu layer increased $F_{0.9\%strain}$ for the YBCO composite by about 5%. For reference, the loads at the elastic limit of the Cu/YBCO and YBCO composites were 1660 N and 1460 N, respectively.

Fig. 3. Load-strain curve for Hastelloy substrate and YBCO and Cu/YBCO composites.

Fig. 4. Variation of I_c/I_{c0} without loading as a function of load applied to YBCO composite with Cu layer.

Fig. 5. Relation between maximum load and number of stress cycles to fracture for YBCO and Cu/YBCO composites.

Fig. 6. Variation of I_c/I_{c0} without loading as a function of number of stress cycles for Cu/YBCO composite.

Fig. 4 shows the variation of I_c/I_{c0} after unloading as a function of the load applied immediately before unloading for the Cu/YBCO composite. Here, I_{c0} is I_c at 0% strain. The irreversible degradation of I_c was first observed at a load of 1940 N, which corresponds to 1.0 % strain. This result indicates that the damage to the YBCO superconducting layer in the Cu/YBCO composite was initiated at this load. The arrow in Fig. 4 indicates the irreversible load for the Cu/YBCO composite, $F_{irr,Cu/YBCOcomp}$. On the other hand, the irreversible load for the YBCO composite, $F_{irr,YBCOcomp}$, was 1730 N. We carried out the following fatigue tests under the load conditions determined from the elastic limit load and the above values of F_{irr} .

Fatigue Property of Cu/YBCO and YBCO Composites

Fig. 5 shows the relationship between the maximum load, F_{max} , and the number of stress cycles to fracture, N_f , for Cu/YBCO and YBCO composites when $R = 0.5$. Arrows pointing to the left indicate F_{irr} for the Cu/YBCO composite, $F_{irr,Cu/YBCOcomp}$, and YBCO composite, $F_{irr,YBCOcomp}$. Arrows pointing to the right attached to symbols indicate the experimental data without fatigue fracture at $N = 10^6$. We defined the load corresponding to each data point as the fatigue strength after 10^6 cycles, $F_{N=10^6}$. For Cu/YBCO and YBCO composites, $F_{N=10^6}$ were 1740 N and 1470 N, respectively. The additional Cu layer increased the value of $F_{N=10^6}$ of the YBCO composite by about 19 % when it is expressed by maximum load.

Fig. 6 shows the change in I_c/I_{c0} during a fatigue test for Cu/YBCO composite when I_c was measured at unloading condition. Here, I_{c0} is I_c before fatigue test. I_c/I_{c0} decreased by over 30 % in the first 2×10^3 cycles when the maximum fatigue load was close to $F_{irr,Cu/YBCOcomp}$ (= 1940 N). This degradation of I_c/I_{c0} corresponds to the static damage to the YBCO superconducting layer. However I_c/I_{c0} did not degrade until the overall fracture of the Cu/YBCO composite occurred when the maximum load was lower than $F_{irr,Cu/YBCOcomp}$ as shown in Fig. 6. These changes in I_c/I_{c0} were attributed to the intrinsic fatigue-insensitive fracture behavior of the YBCO superconducting layer which has ceramic properties.

Fatigue Fracture Mechanism for Cu/YBCO Composite

Our preparatory study on the fatigue fracture of the bare Hastelloy substrate indicated that the fracture surface during early fatigue crack propagation was macroscopically flat and perpendicular to the loading axis. These fracture marks radiated from a nucleus. The fatigue fracture surface was surrounded by a pattern of rough dimples corresponding to the final phase of static fracture during the fatigue cycles. These features were similar to conventional metallic materials [10]. Figs. 7 and 8 show the fracture surface near the onset points of fatigue failure for Cu/YBCO and YBCO composites, respectively. Initial fatigue growth similar to that on the bare Hastelloy substrate was observed at the Hastelloy substrate part of the composite tapes. Arrows show the direction of fatigue crack growth. These observations suggest that overall fatigue fracture on the Cu/YBCO and YBCO composites is caused by fatigue crack onset and growth in the Hastelloy substrate. For the Cu/YBCO composite, fatigue cracks initiated from the lower surface of the Hastelloy substrate as indicated in Fig. 7. For the YBCO composite, some fatigue cracks initiated from the edge of the Hastelloy substrate as shown in Fig. 8. Fatigue cracks in the YBCO composite also initiated from the lower surface of the Hastelloy substrate similar to those indicated in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Fracture surface of Cu/YBCO composite after fatigue test ($F_{max} = 2060$ N, $N_f = 1.3 \times 10^5$). Cu component above solder was delaminated.

Fig. 8. Fracture surface of YBCO composite after fatigue test ($F_{max} = 1530$ N, $N_f = 4.8 \times 10^4$).

Fig.9. Fracture surface of Cu layer after fatigue test on Cu/YBCO composite ($F_{max}=1740$ N, $N_f=1.4\times 10^6$).

In some specimens, fatigue fracture was attributed to fatigue crack initiation in the Cu layer. Fig. 9 shows an example of a fracture surface at $N_f = 1.4 \times 10^6$, where fatigue cracks initiated from the Cu layer. Only the fatigue surface in the Cu layer is shown in this picture. This Cu layer was delaminated from the YBCO composite after the fatigue test, the lower surface of which was in contact with the YBCO composite. This fracture surface was a flat plane perpendicular to the loading axis and fracture marks radiated from a nucleus, which indicate that fatigue cracks initiated from a nucleus on the upper surface of the Cu layer. Arrows indicate the direction of fatigue crack growth. In this nucleus, the original slip plane inclined to the loading axis, which is a typical feature of fatigue crack initiation for ductile metallic materials (so-called stage I)[11]. In the remaining area of Cu surface, the necked region underwent a large reduction of cross-sectional area due to considerable plastic deformation.

Change of Cu properties during Fatigue Loading

For both Cu/YBCO and YBCO composites, fatigue fracture initiated from the Hastelloy substrate after fewer than 10^6 fatigue cycles, while the additional Cu layer resulted in a much higher values of $F_{N=10^6}$. The increase in $F_{N=10^6}$ from the YBCO composite to the Cu/YBCO composite (19 %) is much greater than that of $F_{0.9\%strain}$ under a static load (5 %), as can be seen by comparing Figs. 3 and 5.

Cu component were extracted from Cu/YBCO composites after fatigue tests. Here, the fatigue tests were carried out at $F_{max} = 1720$ N under $R = 0.5$ where the composites do not break at $N = 10^6$ cycles. Tests were interrupted at $N = 10^3$ to 10^6 , and the tensile tests of the extracted Cu were carried out at 77K. Large increase of the yield strength was observed after fatigue cycling, and this increase saturated after 10^5 cycles. The yield strength after 10^5 cycles was about twice as much as that without fatigue loading.

This increase in yield strength of Cu directly contributes to the decrease in applied stress in YBCO and Hastelloy for Cu/YBCO composites. Calculation of change in stress of Hastelloy component was carried out based on the stress-strain curve of Cu at $N = 10^5$

cycles where the increase of the yield strength was saturated. Fig. 10 compares the relations between the stress range of Hastelloy component and number of cycles to failure for Cu/YBCO and YBCO composites. Here, the line in this figure indicates the stress range of Hastelloy component after the consideration of work hardening of Cu. These results suggest that the S-N diagram expressed by the stress component of Hastelloy for Cu/YBCO composites roughly agreed with that of YBCO composites. This fact also confirms that the mechanism of fatigue fracture for Cu/YBCO composites is controlled by the Hastelloy components. However, further detailed researches are necessary because the change in the stress ratio, R , associated with the change of the stress components also contributes to the fatigue properties.

Fig. 10. Relation between stress range of Hastelloy component and number of stress cycles to failure for Cu/YBCO and YBCO composites.

CONCLUSIONS

The additional of a Cu layer to a YBCO composite increased the tensile load at 0.9% strain, $F_{0.9\%strain}$, and the fatigue strength at 10^6 cycles, $F_{N=10^6}$, by 5 % and 19 %, respectively. On the other hand, microscopic observation showed that fatigue fracture in the Cu/YBCO composite mainly initiated from the Hastelloy C-276 substrate, similar to that in the YBCO composite. Fatigue fracture also initiated from the Cu layer, but only when the maximum load was approximately $F_{N=10^6}$. During the fatigue test, the variation in I_c of the Cu/YBCO composite was similar to that observed before the Cu layer was added. No decrease in I_c was observed before overall fatigue fracture occurs when the maximum load in the stress cycles is below $F_{irr,Cu/YBCOcomp}$ (1940 N). The increased properties for Cu/YBCO composites under fatigue loading was attributed to the hardening of Cu component during fatigue loading.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the New Energy and Industrial Technology Development Organization (NEDO), under the Research and Development of Superconducting Magnetic Energy Storage System sponsored by Agency of Natural Resources and Energy, Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry (METI). In addition, YBCO coated conductors used in this work were produced by Chubu Electric Power Co., supported by NEDO through ISTEK, as the Collaborative Research and Development of Fundamental Technologies for Superconductivity Applications.

References

1. K. Higashikawa, T. Nakamura, K. Shikimachi, N. Hirano, S. Nagaya, T. Kiss, M. Inoue, *IEEE Trans. Appl. Supercond.* 17 (2007) 1990.
2. K. Shikimachi, N. Hirano, S. Nagaya, H. Matsuo, G. Nishijima, S. Awaji, K. Watanabe, M. Ishizuka, M. Hamada, *IEEE Trans. Appl. Supercond.* 17 (2007) 2220.
3. S. Noguchi, H. Yamashita, A. Ishiyama, *IEEE Trans. Appl. Supercond.* 13 (2003) 1856.
4. M. Sugano, Y. Yoshida, M. Hojo, K. Shikimachi, N. Hirano, S. Nagaya, *Supercond. Sci. Technol.* 21 (2008) 054006.
5. S. Ochiai, H. Ohno, F. Sekino, Y. Oki, M. Hojo, M. Koganeya, K. Hayashi, Y. Yamada, N. Ayai, K. Watanabe, *Supercond. Sci. Technol.* 12 (1999) 499.
6. M. Hojo, N. Iwasaki, F. Sekino, S. Ochiai, S. Sakai, K. Watanabe, *Cryogenics* 39 (1999) 627.
7. N. Kashima, T. Niwa, M. Mori, S. Nagaya, T. Muroga, S. Miyata, T. Watanabe, Y. Yamada, T. Izumi, Y. Shiohara, *IEEE Trans. Appl. Supercond.* 15 (2005) 2763.
8. M. Sugano, K. Osamura, A. Nyilas, *Supercond. Sci. Technol.* 16 (2003) 1064.
9. A. Nyilas, *Supercond. Sci. Technol.* 18 (2005) S409.
10. S. Bhattacharyya, V. E. Johnson, S. Agarwal, M. A. H. Howes, *IITRI Fracture Handbook, Failure Analysis of Metallic Materials by Scanning Electron Microscopy*, The Metals Research Division IIT Research Institute, Chicago, Illinois, 1979, p.141, 237, 287.
11. T. Duggan, J. Byrne, *Fatigue as a Design Criterion*, The Macmillan Press LTD, London and Basingstoke, 1977, pp.67-72.